

The Art of Tamil Nadu

M. Jency

Research Scholar, Department of History,
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli-627012

Dr. V. Deepthi,

Assistant Professor, Department of History,
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli-627012

ABSTRACT

India is a sizable nation with a rich culture, civilisation, and history. India has a long and prosperous history of civilization, with planned towns, enormous temples, mosques, and cathedrals, palaces, sculptures, paintings, and other artistic works. India is become one of the most well-known tourist destinations in the world thanks to its stunning beauty. Any country's tourism potential is largely influenced by its climate, geography, historical sites, arts, customs, festivals, and society. We can refer to a location as a tourist or pilgrimage centre if it possesses all of these qualities and potentials. Tamil Nadu, a southern Indian state, is a charming place with a long history. It is home to towering temples with exquisite architecture and sculptures, art galleries, and a variety of natural beauties that can be seen on the hills and mountains. Madurai, Rameswaram, Kanyakumari, Tanjavur, Kumbakonam, Trichy, Kancheepuram, Chidambaram, Tiruvannamalai, and Palani are just a few of the numerous cultural, spiritual, and religious destinations in Tamil Nadu. In Tamil Nadu, religious institutions like temples have been actively participating in the religious, social, economic, and cultural lives of the Tamil people.

Key Words: Civilisation, Tourist, Pilgrimage, Spiritual, Temples, Artistic Works

Introduction

Temples were generally built of wood or brick with roofs made variously of timber, thatch or tile in olden times. In some important temples, the roofs were covered with copper to give a more permanent finish. The temple of Nataraja at Chidambaram has preserved this archaic form even to this day. Though the present structure has been renovated in 17th century AD., an ancient mural painting of the Cholas in the Brihadisvara temple, Tanjore (11th century A.D.) shows as it is found today. The temple, with a stone base, has wooden pillars supporting the roof, covered with copper plates gilded with gold, and hence, it is called the golden hall, Ponnambalam.

In the southernmost region of Tamilnadu, in the Kanyakumari District, and the neighbouring Kerala State, where temples today are typically buildings with tiled roofs, the name ambalam, which means "temple," is frequently used. The metal tiles are occasionally more artistic, but they are typically more plain and rectangular in design. These temples might have two or three levels. Some temples gained more significance through time in the course of religious history. Great kings considered it their responsibility to shower them with wealth and decorate the roofs in gold. Several Chola rulers were proud of their gold-covered Nataraja temple in Chidambaram. This practise persisted even in the instance of the Vishnu temple.

Cave temples

In the northern and southern regions of Tamilnadu, respectively, the Pallavas and their great contemporaries, the Pandyas, have left behind a sizable number of excavated cave temples. Two amazing cave-temples at Namakkal in the Salem District have been unearthed almost simultaneously by the Atiyamans, a family of petty kings. From the most basic, single-celled cave to a more sophisticated kind with one or more sanctums flanked by mandapa or mandapas, the layout of the cave-temples varies. The sanctum is hollowed out at the back wall of the majority of them, which are rectangular pillared halls. The sanctum or sanctums may occasionally be positioned on the lateral sides, while other times they may be excavated in the back wall. The mandapa (pillared pavilion) that still exists today is the principal architectural inspiration for the cave temples.day in various parts of Tamilnadu. They are mostly pillared pavilions, used for village assemblies, festivals, or exposition of

various texts. There are evidences to show that such pillared mandapas, housing deity existed in the Pallava period, as in the case of Uttaramerur in Chingleput District which served as a meeting place of the village assemblies. It is note-worthy that the excavated cave-temples are called mandapas in inscriptions and local tradition,

Among the Pallava rulers, the first to excavate a large number of cave- temples was Mahendra I (590-630): these are found from Madras in the north to Trichy in the south. A number of these cave-temples are inscribed with his titles. In the cave-temple at Mandagapattu, he states that the temple was caused to be made by him, without the use of wood, brick, metal or mortar. The cave-temple at Trichy is perhaps the finest example having a remarkable sculpture of Siva. Of the Pallava kings after Mahendra I one who has left a great number of monuments, is Rajasimha, also known as Narasimha, the author of all the monuments of Mamallapuram. The Cave-temples found at Mamallapuram. show a variety of forms; in fact, each one is a type by itself the most remarkable of them are the Mahishamardini cave, the Varaha cave, the Adivaraha cave, and the Trimurti cave. These caves have sculptures, which have attained international fame. Not far away from Mamallapuram, there stands a unique rock-cut cave, excavated by the same king Its facade is adorned with a row of Yali heads though the cave has been left somewhat unfinished. In the beginning of 9th Century AD., a few cave temples were excavated near Trichy and in the Pudukkottai region, in the reign of the Pallava Danti- varman.

In the far south, an excavated cave-temple at Pillaiyarpatti in Ramnad District, is of importance. It is dedicated to Siva and carries three sculptures An Inscription inside the excavated cave, in the characters of the sixth century A.D. may show that the cave has also to be assigned to that period.

Two cave-temples, one dedicated to Siva and the other to Vishnu, In Thirumeyyam, are assigned to 7th century A.D. Besides these, a few other cave- temples in the same region also belong to the same period. The Pandya Parantaka Nedunjadayan (8th century AD) was a great patron and during his reign came the cave-temple in Thirupparankunram, and Anamalai hills, both near Madurai, Excavating cave-temples in rock which was in vogue from 6th to 9th Century AD, was given up in the succeeding ages. Most of the cave-temples were dedicated to either Siva, or Vishnu. Some are dedicated to two or more deities, as Brahma, Vishnu, Siva, Subramanya, Durga or Ganapati. A few enshrine Jaina sages like Adinatha or

Mahavira. However, no cave-temple has so far been noticed in Tamilnadu dedicated to the Buddhist faith.

Monolithic Temples

Temples have been cut out from standing rocks at Mamallapuram, by the Pallavas. They show various forms that were prevalent before the period. The group of five temples cut out from standing rocks at Mamallapuram familiarly called Pancapandava Rathas, are unique creations of the Pallavas and are the greatest attractions of the Tamil country. Four temples in one row were probably cut out from a single rock that extended from south to the north. Of them, the tallest is the three-storeyed temple, the Dharmaraja-ratha with an octagonal sikhara and a garbhagriha in each storey. It is called Atyanthakama Pallaveswara Griham in the inscription and must have been a Saiva shrine originally. It carries lovely sculptures in the upper tiers, and the titles of the Pallava ruler Rajasimha, the creator of all the monuments of Mamallapuram are found inscribed on the wall as well. The next one has a wagon-vaulted roof and is popularly called Bhima-ratha. Probably it enshrined an image of Vishnu in his reclining form. The third is a small two-storeyed temple, the Arjuna-ratha, with a small frontal mandapa and bears lovely sculptures, around the sanctum wall. The fourth in the line is a simple hut-shaped temple dedicated to Goddess Korraival (Durgal). The form is called the Kuta or Parnasala type of Vimana. Standing away from these four temples is an apsidal shrine called Sahadeva-ratha: it is this type which is called Thunganai Madam, in Tamil and Gajaprishta, (back of the elephant) in Sanskrit and as if to remind of this similarity an elephant is shown standing nearby.

These five temples show five different types of temples that were in existence. Besides these, there is to the north of the Arjuna's penance, a nearly- finished monolith, called Ganesa-ratha. It is a rectangular sala type of temple, originally dedicated to Siva but now housing an image of Ganesa. An inscription states that this was caused to be made by Pallava Atyantakama. At the western end of the village, there are monoliths standing side by side called two Pidarirathas and the third called Valayan Kuttai-ratha. All the monoliths of the Pallavas are located only in Mamallapuram. In front of the Mahishamardini cave, there is a rock showing the beginning of this type of architecture. All these monoliths though almost all of them left unfinished were created by Rajasimha, who bore the title Atyantakama, during

the first quarter of the 8th Century A.D. Two of them bear his inscriptions and are named after him.

In the far south in the Pandya territory, there stands a monolith known as Vettuvan-Kovil at Kazhugumalai. Its method of cutting differs from that of the Pallavas, for at Kazhugumalai a part of the hill has been separated from the parent rock for carving out the monolith, which is also left unfinished.

Structural Temples

The structural temples have various forms and are in different media. However, the most of them are built of brick and stone. But no brick temple that could be definitely dated earlier than 8th Century A.D., has yet been found. Among the stone temples, the earliest yet to survive is the one at Kuram, built in the 7th Century A.D., only a part of this structure is extant. The temples to survive in their entirety are those erected by Rajasimha Pallava, at Mamallapuram, Kanchipuram and Panamalai in the 8th Century A.D.

As mentioned earlier, temples built prior to 7th Century A.D. were of brick, and were decorated with painted stucco figures on the outer walls. It is undoubtedly the Pallavas who started employing stone for the entire construction, from the base to the top. Such all-stone temples came to be called Karrali in Tamil. As these were copied from brick structures, the Pallavas initially chose sandstone (a soft stone) and imitated the stucco art in the exterior decoration. The walls were erected with plain cut slabs and the sculptures were carved on the walls itself imitating the stucco technique. Later the entire walls and the sculptures were covered with thin coat of lime, and then painted. Once painted, hardly any difference could be discerned between the brick and the stone temples.

Most of the structural temples of the Pallavas are found at Kanchi. The best to survive is the celebrated Kailasanatha, the most elaborate and the finest of all the Pallava structural temples. It is a creation of Rajasimha who has also left the Sea Shore temple at Mamallapuram and the temple on the top of Panamalai hill. A few other temples in Kanchi are also assigned to his period. During his reign, the tower above the sanctum was given the most conspicuous form. In front of the Kailasanatha, Rajasimha's son Mahendravarman III and queens have erected small temples of great beauty. A temple in Thiruppattur near

Tiruchi, bears very close resemblance to this Kailasanatha temple of Kanchi and has to be assigned to the same ruler.

The successors of Rajasimha have continued the temple-building tradition. The most noteworthy temple of this period is the Valkuntanatha temple at Kanchi, the Sundaravarada temple at Uttaramerur and others. The Sundaravarada temple has a stone base above which rises the brick structure. Soon the Pallavas abandoned sand-stone and started building with granite, and in the new material, the exterior decorations were reduced to the minimum. A number of such small temples like the ones at Thiruttani, Takkolam, Alambakkam and others were built in the Pallava territory.

The Cholas who established themselves in about 850 AD., were great builders. Initially their temples, built of granite stone, were of modest proportions. A temple, named after Vijayalaya, who established the Chola empire, at Nartamalai is perhaps the earliest of the Chola surviving temples. Vijayalaya's son Aditya was also a great builder, and is said to have built a number of stone temples along the banks of the river Kaviri. Quite a good number of his temples have survived: they are all modest in size but remarkable for their proportions and sculptural wealth. The Nageswara temple of Kumbakonam, the Koranganatha temple of Srinivasanallur, the Siva temple at Pullamangai and the twin temples at Paluvur are landmarks of this period. It is worth noting that the temple at the last mentioned place was built by a Paluvettaraiyar chieftain, Avanikandarpan, a subordinate of the Chola king Aditya. Aditya's son, Parantaka has also left a number of temples which follow closely the tradition set up by Aditya but these are somewhat less elaborate. As a matter of fact, the successors of Parantaka followed the same form and idiom in the construction of the temple. But a great change ushered in with the accession of Rajaraja, the Great, in A.D. 985. The Mention must be made here of the three temples of Kodumbalur, of which two have survived and the third represented only by the base. group built by Puti, an Irukkuvel chieftain occupies an important position in the history of the temple-architecture in the 10th Century.

The Chola temples of 10th Century have modest heights. 30 feet on an average. They were built of stone from base to the top. While in some cases, stone was employed up to the ceiling above which the superstructure was built of brick and mortar, The most common types are with square, octagonal and circular sikharas A series of small panels depicting scenes from Ramayana and Sivapurana are portrayed in the base, some temples carry the

portraits of the builders on the walls. Quite often the temple has a group of small shrines erected around the main sanctum to house the secondary deities.

Rajaraja the Great (985-1014) was the greatest of all the Chola emperors. Befitting his magnificent personality, he built, entirely in granite the Great Temple of Tanjore rising to about 200 feet in height. This is the tallest and the greatest stone temple of Tamil Nadu, luckily well preserved. This seems to, have been modelled on the lines of Virattanesvara temple at Thiruvadigal which was a Pallava foundation of 7th Century and renovated in 9th. It is built of stone up to the base and the superstructure is of brick But the great temple of Tanjore has been built entirely of granite in a place where stone is very scarce. The massive superstructure of the temple is supported by two solid granite walls and the stupendous height has been achieved by corbelling an incredible feat on the part of the architects and craftsmen of that period. The sanctum tower of the Tanjore temple was the tallest and the most magnificent piece of architecture ever built in India. Rajaraja's son and successor Rajendra, followed the foot-steps of his father and designed a more ambitious temple at Gangaikondacholapuram. Though this is little shorter in height than that of Tanjore it has some beautiful sculptures of superb workmanship.

Other Chola rulers Kulottunga 1. Rajaraja II and Kulottunga III have built monumental temples but of lesser dimensions. The Rajarajesvaram temple at Darasuram, and the Thribhuvanaviresvara temple at Thribhuvanam, are the outstanding monuments of the later Cholas.

It was a period when the towers above the vimanas held the dominant position. The sculptures fitted into the framework, are subordinated to architectural form. If the Pallavas were great sculptors, the Cholas were great architects. In the Pallava tradition even a temple looks like a piece of lovely sculpture while in a Chola edifice the plastic embellishments are considerably outshone architecture. With the Cholas ended the tradition of building lofty sanctum-towers and gradually the emphasis was shifted to the towers above the gateways called.

Gopuras

Gopuras or entrance-towers adorning the temples evolved from simple tiled-roof entrances, having a raised frontal opening. Such primitive gopuras are found even to this day

mostly in the southernmost part of the Tamil country. What was once a functional opening soon became an ornamental adjunct of gigantic dimensions. The earliest gopuras made in stone, are found in Pallava temples where they are small in dimensions and often single-storied. Such gopuras, called dvarasalas are found both in front and rear of the temple. The extant gopuras of the early Cholas are made of stone up to the ceiling above which rises the brick-built superstructure. Originally the entire structure was built of stone. They show only two dvarapalas, adorning the lower portion.

With the advent of Rajaraja in 11th Century we find a new turn in the history of the gopuras: two gopuras placed in one alignment in front of the vimana, the inner one smaller than the outer, became the norm. This tradition continued up to the end of the 12th Century as it is to be seen in Darasuram and Tribhuvanam. The gopuras of this type are broad based and are short with shrine chambers in the lower tier.

In the 12th Century a new trend of erecting four gopuras, one in each cardinal direction came to the scene, the gopuras of Chidambaram providing the best example. The lower tier of the gopura is of stone while the upper part is of brick. The stone-built tier is divided into two horizontal bays, "each bay carrying a number of niches. The lower row of niches carry sculptures of minor deities, while the upper ones enshrine various aspects of Siva to whom the temple is dedicated. The western gopura of Chidambaram and the outer gopura of Darasuram carry lable inscriptions Another interesting feature of these gopuras are the series of dance panels, representing various karanas from Bharata's Natya Sastra in the door jambs. The tradition continued for quite some time. But towards the end of 12th Century A.D. Kulottunga III the Chola, introduced rearing yali-motif along the lower tier. His Gopuras are found in a number of places among which the ones at Tribhuvanam and Thiruvarur are outstanding ones.

The Pandyas of the late 13th Century introduced a seated lion at the base of the pilasters of the gopura walls. As times rolled on, a number of enclosures were added and likewise gopuras at each entra.

Mandapas

A number of mandapas, (pillared pavilions) were added to the temples among which, the front mandapa, the 100 pillared mandapa, the thousand pillared mandapa, and the Kalyana

mandapas are to be seen frequently in great temples. These mandapas fulfilled a variety of functions, from the performance of sacred ablutions to the exposition of various sciences. Though the mandapas In the Pallava temples stood separately from the main sanctum, in the Chola period, they were integrated into the Vimana. The front mandapas that originally adorned the great temples of Tanjore and Gangaikondacholapuram, were probably two-tiered. But the most beautiful of all the Chola mandapa to have survived is the one at Darasuram, built in 12th Century AD., by Rajaraja II Vijayanagar art, and the second from the celebrated "Horse Court" in the Sri- rangam temple, created in the 17th century, a century later than the first example. The walls enclosing the temple complex, called "prakara walls have " evolved with the times. An early example is a curious one and has not been imitated since. Fig 45a shows the "prakara" walls of the Kailasanatha temple at Kanchipuram, made up of a number of small shrines. On the outside these walls carry sculptures of horse and rider. Belonging to a much more usual type is that of the Srirangam temple. Some of the bigger temples had their "prakara" walls built in two storeys, as at Gangaikondacholapuram. The Hindu artists fastened upon many areas in a temple.

Conclusion

The thematic treatment includes a wide variety of themes, most of them often changing and deviating from the silpa accounts and thereby setting new norms. It may be added that the temple cars constitute an important area for iconographical research. This is mainly because much of the unique data found in the cars is unpublished and not even correctement documenté, except for the papers listed under the reference.

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